

More power for less money: Statistical, power, and cost analyses that account for intracluster correlation in experiments with same-group cage-mates

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ABSTRACT

In experiments with co-housed animals, outcome variables can become correlated among cage-mates. This is called intracluster correlation. When cage-mates are all of the same group, the experiment is like a cluster randomized trial in human studies. Intracluster correlation in same-group cage-mates experiments is a type of pseudoreplication and ignoring it in statistical analyses increases false positive results. Here, we provide a tutorial on how to account for intracluster correlation in the statistical analyses. Specifically, this is done by including cage identifiers as an independent variable in a linear mixed model – a type of ANOVA. Since power analyses must be based on the planned statistical analyses, we also include effect size calculations and sample size calculations (types of power analyses) in the tutorial. Effect size and sample size calculations help assure regulatory committees, like IACUCs, granting agencies, and journals, that experiments are properly powered. These calculations will show us that designing experiments to have more cages and fewer animals per cage is more efficient than fewer cages with more animals per cage. This statistical efficiency, which means more power, can be translated into reduced animal numbers – one of the 3Rs of animal research. We then perform cost analyses and show how the costs of more cages with fewer animals overall are often cheaper than the costs of fewer cages with more animals overall. Altogether, accounting for intracluster correlation in the experiment design and analysis of same-group cage-mates experiments results in fewer statistical errors, reduced costs and fewer animals. Finally, we demonstrate the analyses using JASP, a free, open-source, user-friendly statistical software, and provide R and SAS code to perform the analyses.

INTRODUCTION

In many biomedical experiments using animals, the animals in the same cage (or enclosure or tank) must be or are of the same experimental group; for example, cage-mates have the same diet or cage-mates all receive the same individually administered substance. This “same-group cage-mates” characteristic is part of the experiment design – how the controlled, known, and unknown factors are positioned with the animals in space, time, and possibly other dimensions. Examples of controlled factors are treatments, doses, developmental ages, time points, and possibly sex; examples of known factors are cage, birth or shipment cohort, litter or siblings, and source of injected diseased cells or viruses; examples of unknown factors are temperature, noise, and light gradients, and human error. A good experiment design leverages the controlled and known factors to increase statistical precision and accuracy of results; and

good experimental procedures, like randomization and blinding, guard against biases from unknown factors. Sometimes, researchers focus their experiment design on the controlled factors, and inadvertently or unknowingly ignore known factors when designing their experiments. For example, processing all of one treatment group on one day and all of the control group on a different day; here, processing day is a known factor and should be considered when designing the experiment. The resulting experiment design can be suboptimal. Furthermore, when statistically analyzing the data, researchers inadvertently or unknowingly leave known factors out of the statistical model, and this can cause statistical errors in the results, specifically, Type I or Type II errors, also known as false positive or false negative results, respectively. For example, unknowingly leaving cage identifiers out of the statistical model when comparing diets (administered at the cage-level) could lead to increased false positive results (Type I errors); or inadvertently leaving litter identifiers out of the model when comparing genotypes among littermates could lead to increased false negative results (Type II errors). In this work, we will consider animal experiments that have the same-group cage-mates characteristic, and we will illustrate how the knowable factor, cage, should be incorporated into statistical analyses. Since power analyses are based on the statistical analysis, we will illustrate how to calculate the difference between an experimental mean and control mean (standardized by the standard deviation) which is detectable for a desired power level; this is an effect size calculation – a type of power analysis. We will also illustrate how to compute sample sizes for a desired power level – another type of power analysis. These power analyses illustrations will also show how to distribute same-group animals among the cages to increase statistical power. Specifically, we will show that having more cages with fewer animals per cage (“more-cages & fewer-animals”) is a statistically more powerful design than having fewer cages with more animals per cage (“fewer-cages & more-animals”). When sample size calculations (as opposed to effect size calculations) are performed before the experiment begins, we will demonstrate cost analyses comparing equally powered experiments, one with more-cages & fewer-animals and the other with fewer-cages & more-animals. And we will see from this cost analysis demonstration that experiments with more-cages & fewer-animals tend to cost less than a power-equivalent experiment with fewer-cages & more-animals.

Same-group cage-mates experiments are connected to a broader literature. The same-group cage-mates characteristic in animal experiment designs is similar to clusters in cluster randomized trials (and the similar “individually randomized group-treatment trials”) conducted in humans. The problems of ignoring clusters in statistical analyses of cluster randomized trials are well established,^{25,27} and directly translate to ignoring cages in statistical analyses of same-group cage-mates experiments. The root problem of ignoring clusters in statistical analyses is the violation of the independent observations assumption on which usual statistical analyses are based. (Independent observations means that the responses from any two subjects are not related in any way.) In human studies, it is well known that measures of an outcome variable from subjects in the same cluster tend to become or are correlated.^{4,26} This correlation of outcomes among members of the same cluster is called “intracluster correlation”, which we denote with ρ . A potentially relatable example is how educational outcomes among schoolmates tend to be more similar than among students from other schools; that is, the educational outcomes among schoolmates may become correlated. Another example is how clinical outcomes of patients treated by the same psychologist (who is to deliver a particular therapy) will be more alike than to outcomes from patients treated by another psychologist who is delivering the same therapy; that is, the clinical outcomes among patients from the same psychologist may be correlated.

Ignoring clusters in the statistical analysis of cluster randomized trials, and thus pooling all the subjects in each treatment group, may result in a sacrificial pseudoreplication error, as described in Hurlbert's seminal article on pseudoreplication (focused in ecology) and as noted for cluster randomized trials in Dransfield & Brightwell.^{13,8} Likewise, in same-group cage-mates experiments, intraclass correlation can develop among cage-mates and ignoring cage in analyses can result in the same sorts of statistical errors noted in human studies.

When the observed outcomes of cage-mates are correlated (i.e., have intraclass correlation), the assumption of independent observations is violated, and the violation of this assumption results in statistical errors. In animal experiments (and not just those with the same-group cage-mates characteristic), non-0 intraclass correlation manifests as cage-to-cage variability, or simply cage variability. For experiments with same-group cage-mates, ignoring that cage variability in the statistical analysis can cause an increase in Type I error rates (i.e., false positive rates).¹⁶ Similarly, ignoring intraclass correlation can cause increased Type I error rates in clinical,²⁵ educational,³⁸ livestock,³³ crop,³¹ and cellular studies.¹¹ Increased Type I error rates means that the p -values tend to be artificially too small. Accounting for cage variability in the statistical analysis keeps the p -values correct (i.e., keeps the Type I error rate at the desired level, such as 0.05). The magnitude of the cage variability impacts the power of the study; as cage variability goes up, power goes down. Consequently, considering cage variability in the planning stages of an experiment is particularly useful. Since the sample size calculations from the power analysis depend on cage variability, the cost analyses also depend on cage variability: increased sample sizes (due to cage variability) means increased costs.

The notion of accounting for cage in both the planning and statistical analysis phases of experiments is also noted in guidelines for "Animal Research: Reporting In Vivo Experiments" (ARRIVE). The ARRIVE 2.0 guidelines help researchers know what issues are vital when addressing the 3Rs of animal research – Replace, Refine, Reduce, and how to rigorously address those issues (<https://arriveguidelines.org/arrive-guidelines>). In particular, the updated ARRIVE 2.0 guidelines point out that cage may need to be considered as an independent (or predictor) variable in the statistical analyses, and that the cage may also be the experimental unit instead of individual animals. The explanation and elaboration of ARRIVE 2.0 contains the Essential 10 and Recommended Set of elements to report on and has several examples.³⁰

For studies where members of a cluster are of the same experimental condition (e.g., same-group cage-mates), others have covered statistical, power, and cost analyses. For example, statistical analyses are provided for educational studies,³⁸ for cellular studies (among others),¹¹ in livestock studies,² and in crops.²⁹ Statistical and power analyses are provided in a variety of human studies,²⁵ in clinical trials,³ and in livestock trials.⁶ Cost analyses have been considered using education and clinical examples,^{24,23} and for agriculture studies.⁹ The reference lists on the National Institute of Health's Research Methods Resources for cluster-randomized trials and individually randomized group-treatment trials is particularly useful for understanding the work done on statistical, power, and cost analyses, but the references are focused on human studies.²⁷ We did not find any references that covered all three analysis types – statistical, power, and cost – in the same work; nor did we find any that covered any of these analysis types in biomedical animal experiments except for our previous article.¹⁶

For the statistical and power analyses, we provide a tutorial using JASP (version 0.18.3) – an open source, free, statistical software designed for non-statisticians,¹⁴ and in the

Supplementary Material provide R and SAS code for conducting the statistical analyses. The figures and tables were produced in R (version 4.4.2), and we provide instructions so that new-to-R users might adapt the code for their own purpose and run in web-based R browsers;³² this also is in the Supplementary Material.

Same-group cage-mates experiment example

A typical same-group cage-mates experiment will have 2 or more experimental groups, with multiple same-group animals sharing a cage; see [Figure 1](#) for a mouse example. The animals will then be co-housed for some length of time, whether a day or two or much longer. This distinguishing characteristic of same-group cage-mates is important for choosing appropriate statistical analyses. A usual statistical analysis of the outcomes measured on each animal is an analysis of variance (ANOVA). When there are only 2 groups, an independent samples *t*-test is a usual choice and is a special case of an ANOVA. The assumptions of the ANOVA are these: (i) the groups are independent of each other; (ii) the outcome is normal in distribution; (iii) the standard deviation (SD) is the same for all groups; and (iv) the observed outcomes from the animals in a group are independent of each other. The first assumption (i) may be checked with a clear description of the experimental groups. We can, and many do, use the data (specifically, the residuals or differences of actual from predicted values; *not* the actual values alone) to check the normal and constant SD assumptions (ii and iii). With an appropriate statistical analysis that incorporates cage identifiers, we can also use the data to check the independent observations assumption (iv).

Rack	Col 1	Col 2	Col 3
Row 1	D D	E E	C C
	D D	E E	C C
Row 2	E E	D D	C C
	E E	D D	C C

Figure 1. 24 same-sex, unrelated mice of the same age were equally randomized to treatment groups, C, D, and E. The first 4 mice randomized to a group were individually administered the treatment and placed in the same cage; the last 4 randomized to the group were similarly treated and caged. The 6 cages were then randomized on the rack.

STATISTICAL ANALYSES

The data. [Figure 1](#) displays and describes the design for a hypothetical experiment of treatments for female mice infected with chlamydia. The controlled factor is vaccine: C – a vehicle control, and D and E – two active vaccines under study. The known factor is cage. Randomization of mice to treatment and cages on the rack reduce or eliminate any bias from unknown factors. For each mouse, we record a unique animal identifier, the treatment to which it was allocated, the uniquely identified cage in which the mouse was housed, and the observed values of the outcome variables. We simulated outcome variables, *NK* – the percentage of natural killer cells in the oviducts, and *CD4* – the percentage of central memory CD4 cells in the spleen. For the *NK* outcome, we also simulated the situation where it was not possible to obtain a value for some mice (for example, the tissue sample was of low quality). These example data are found in [Figure 2](#) and in the JASP file in the Supplementary Material.

An ANOVA model. For the data collected in our typical same-group cage-mates experiment, many first consider a one-way ANOVA having this statistical model,

$$Y_{tm} = TRT_t + mouse_{t(m)}, \quad (1)$$

where

- Y is the outcome variable (here, either NK or $CD4$); the value to be statistically analyzed.
- TRT is an abbreviation for treatment and is a fixed factor; that is, a factor that we are particularly interested in and want the estimates for each of its t levels (here, the levels are vaccines C, D, and E).
- $mouse$ is a random factor; that is, we know the outcome will vary among the mice, and there is no mouse that we and the scientific community are interested in. This random factor is the biological “error term.” There are m mice within a treatment group (thus the $t(m)$ subscript notation), and m can differ among the treatment groups. We assume the standard deviation of $mouse$ is σ_A , where the subscript A stands for animal

(We note that TRT may be combinations of other fixed factors; for example, factors A and B . Then TRT can be rewritten as $A + B + A \times B$, for which a two-way ANOVA is also appropriate.) When the ANOVA assumptions are met, an ANOVA is an appropriate way to analyze the data. But when cage-mates are of the same treatment group, then ANOVA’s independent observations assumption may be violated. When we record and use cage identifiers in the analyses, we can check this assumption. Regardless, cage is a known factor in the experiment design and a proper statistical analysis will (at least initially) include cage identifier in the model.

A Linear Mixed Model (LMM). The model is

$$Y_{tcm} = TRT_t + cage_{t(c)} + mouse_{tc(m)}, \quad (2)$$

where

- Y and TRT are as in Eqn 1.
- $cage$ is a random factor; that is, a factor that can be a source of variability, but we and the scientific community are not interested in the estimates for individual cages. There are c cages nested within a given treatment level (thus the $t(c)$ subscript notation), and c can differ among the different treatment levels.
- $mouse$ is a random factor, as in Eqn 1. But there are m mice nested within a cage (thus the $tc(m)$ subscript notation), and m can differ among the cages.

This model assumes the cages are independent of each other (that the observed outcomes of mice in one cage are not affected by animals or conditions in other cages) and that the cage means (based on the mice within the cage) are normally distributed with a standard deviation of σ_C , where the subscript C stands for cage. The $cage_{t(c)}$ term is equivalent to assuming each cage has its own intercept; this note is relevant to specifying the correct model in JASP and other statistical software. We additionally note that the σ_C parameter will be needed for power analyses described below (we will transform σ_C into ρ , the intraclass correlation). This model also assumes observed outcomes from the mice are normal in distribution with a standard deviation of σ_A . This model is called a linear mixed model (LMM) because it has a mix of fixed effects (here TRT) and random effects (here $cage$), instead of only one random effect for the individually observed outcome variable (from individual *mice*).

Some additional technical notes for fitting the LMM: We first sort the data so that the rows of data from cage-mates are stacked on top of each other; this can help the computational efficiency of the statistical software when fitting the LMM. REML estimation of the variance components is generally recommended.²¹ When available in the statistical software, we estimate the error degrees of freedom with the Kenward-Roger method,¹⁵ and we allow the variances to be unbounded. Kenward-Roger's method gives improved estimates of variances and degrees of freedom, especially in small sized samples. Also in small sized samples, allowing variances to be unbounded improves Type I error rates.²⁸ However, some software programs do not have the Kenward-Roger method available, and in those instances, we use Satterthwaite's method. Also, some software programs do not allow for unbounded (i.e., negative) variances. JASP, the software we illustrate below uses REML as its default estimation method, but it does not fully implement the Kenward-Roger method, so we use Satterthwaite's method. JASP also does not yet allow for unbounded variances.

Example 1: Non-negligible cage variability

This example illustrates analyses of an outcome variable, *NK* (Figure 2), for which the cage variability may not be negligible. We first fit the LMM (Eqn 2) and highlight important points in the results. Then we fit the ANOVA (Eqn 1) and contrast its results with those from the LMM. (We will use gray highlight to signify words and text in the JASP modules.)

In JASP, we switch to JASP analyses mode with the Analyses tab. Then, within the Mixed Models tab, we use the dropdown menu to choose Classical → Linear Mixed Models. We select *NK* as the Dependent variable; *TRT* goes into the Fixed effects variables; and *CageID* goes into Random effects grouping factors. Note that *CageID* is a unique identifier for each cage, and thus uniquely identifies all the random "groups."

Expanding the Model field, we leave the Model components and Random effects at their default settings.

Expanding the model's Options field, we leave the Type of sums of squares for testing the fixed factors at the default value of III and the Test method at its default of Satterthwaite. (Though the Kenward-Roger method is an option here, JASP does not currently implement the Kenward-Roger method for making pairwise comparisons, which we describe further down.) This Satterthwaite option is important as it ensures the correct degrees of freedom are computed. For viewing results, we select Model summary, which displays the ANOVA summary table, and, importantly, the Variance/correlation estimates, which displays the estimates of σ_C and σ_A . We leave the other options up to the user.

We leave the Plots field for the user to explore but will recommend setting the Confidence interval method to Model or None. Model provides confidence intervals based on the same assumptions (namely equal variances among treatment groups) on which the *F*- and *t*-tests are based.

We are usually interested in obtaining the Estimated marginal means for the treatment groups, so we move *TRT* from Model variables to Selected variables and change Estimate df option to Satterthwaite to match with Test method in the Options field. (The Kenward-Roger method is not yet available for this portion of the JASP analysis.) Since often, there are specific

comparisons we want to make among the different treatments, we need to Specify contrasts (or comparisons) of interest. Figure 3 shows all 3 pairwise comparisons among treatments C, D, and E, and includes a fourth contrast to show how these contrasts may be used to make other comparisons of interest. When there are multiple contrasts, we will need to consider options for P-value adjustment: for this work however, we choose None. Westfall et al. describe different considerations when choosing a *p*-value adjustment method.³⁵

	MouseID	TRT	CageID	NK	NKmiss	CD4
1	10	C	1.1	10.72	10.72	25.09
2	18	C	1.1	8.51		24.47
3	64	C	1.1	6.52		18.23
4	67	C	1.1	11.54	11.54	24.16
5	13	C	2.2	8.51	8.51	26.96
6	16	C	2.2	8.04	8.04	24.78
7	29	C	2.2	6.52	6.52	22.28
8	62	C	2.2	8.86	8.86	25.4
9	3	D	1.2	6.64		25.71
10	35	D	1.2	8.39	8.39	27.9
11	61	D	1.2	8.51	8.51	30.39
12	70	D	1.2	7.11	7.11	37.26
13	8	D	2.1	8.16	8.16	25.71
14	11	D	2.1	6.64		27.59
15	39	D	2.1	7.92		28.52
16	79	D	2.1	7.69	7.69	31.33
17	7	E	1.3	5.47	5.47	22.91
18	23	E	1.3	3.14	3.14	21.04
19	60	E	1.3	4.77	4.77	20.1
20	83	E	1.3	7.81		22.91
21	26	E	2.3	7.22		26.96
22	36	E	2.3	5.82		18.85
23	54	E	2.3	7.69	7.69	16.67
24	66	E	2.3	7.81	7.81	24.78
25						

Figure 2. Data for Examples 1 and 2 in the JASP data editor.

Specify contrasts P-value adjustment None ▼

Add Contrast
Delete Contrast
Reset

	TRT	Contrast 1	Contrast 2	Contrast 3	Contrast 4
1	C	1	1	0	1
2	D	-1	0	1	-0.5
3	E	0	-1	-1	-0.5

Figure 3. From the Estimate marginal means field, we must specify the comparisons of interest, or “contrasts.” Here, we make all pairwise comparisons among treatments C, D, and E in Contrasts 1 – 3, then compare the average of treatments D and E to the mean of C in Contrast 4.

Because our treatment levels are categorical and not quantitative, like a dose or time interval, we cannot use the Estimated trends/conditional slopes field. This field can be useful if your treatment levels are quantitative, but that is beyond the scope of this work; see Lazic.¹⁷

Example 1 results from the recommended analysis

Important points. There are two results that are important to notice. First, we look to Variance/Correlation Estimates to see that σ_C is estimated to be 0.599 percentage points (see CageID: Variance Estimates). This means that cage variability may, indeed, be non-negligible, that the measures from animals within the same cage may have become correlated; thus, violating the independent observations assumption. Second to notice is the error degrees of freedom (DF) on the F and t tests. (The error DF on the F statistic is the denominator DF.) Though there were 24 mice going into the analysis, the error DF is much lower, 3 in this example. (Technical note: Since this is a balanced design, the error $DF = (c - 1)t$, where c is the number of cages in a treatment ($c = 2$), and t is the number of treatment groups ($t = 3$.) That is because the Satterthwaite method correctly recognizes the presence of cage variability and treats cage as the experimental unit and mouse as the observational unit (see Lazic et al. for a discussion of experimental and observational units).¹⁸

Contrast from ANOVA results. Regarding the comparisons we made among treatment groups, let’s consider the largest pairwise difference – Contrast 2, which is the difference between the Treatment C and Treatment E means. The estimated difference is 2.436 percentage points with $t_3 = 2.623$ and $p = 0.079$. Though close to the traditional 0.05 significance level, it isn’t significant. Ignoring CageID in the usual ANOVA, the resulting comparison assumes all observations are independent of all other observations and returns a $t_{21} = 3.269$ and $p = 0.004$. It seems appealing to get the lower p -value with the ANOVA, but this analysis (ignoring cage variability when it is non-negligible) is documented to have inflated Type I error rates as cage SD, σ_C , increases; that is, you think the Type I error rate is 0.05, but because of assumption violations, it can be notably higher.¹⁶

Results when data are missing. When data are missing completely at random (that is, there is no systematic reason why the data are missing), the same LMM described above gives a correct analysis. We analyzed *NKmiss*, which are the same data as *NK* (analyzed above) with some values deleted completely at random. The results are the same with respect to statistical inferences: cage variability may still be non-negligible; the Satterthwaite method still computes the error DF treating cage as the experimental unit; and Contrast 2 is still not statistically significant with the LMM analysis but significant with a one-way ANOVA. A result that may confuse some are the error DF for the contrasts: the error DF are not integers. Though often DF are integers, they may take on any value greater than or equal to 1. Satterthwaite's method produces error DF estimates, and sometimes those estimates are not integers.

Example 2: Negligible cage variability

This example illustrates analyses of an outcome variable, *CD4*, for which the cage variability may be negligible. Because the cage variability is estimated to be negligible, we will see that the LMM (Eqn 2) returns the same results as ANOVA (Eqn 1).

In JASP, to analyze *CD4* with the LMM, we simply replace *NKmiss* with *CD4* as the **Dependent variable** at the top of the **Linear Mixed Models** module; everything else is the same.

Example 2 results from recommended analysis

Important points. As with Example 1, we first look to the **Variance/Correlation Estimates** and see that σ_C is estimated to be 0 (see **CageID: Variance Estimates**). This means that cage variability may, indeed, be negligible, that the measures of this particular outcome from the animals within the same cage may have not become correlated, and that the independent observations assumption for ANOVA is reasonable. Thus, Satterthwaite's method does no correction to the error DF, and the results are the same as from the ANOVA. Since the LMM gives the same results as the ANOVA model when cage variability may be negligible, and adjusts the results when cage variability may be non-negligible, then we see that there is no need to run the ANOVA model.

POWER ANALYSES

We will simplify the power analyses to the independent samples *t*-test – a special case of the ANOVA in Eqn 1 and LMM in Eqn 2. We do this for two reasons. One reason is that, often, there is at least one pair of populations the researcher wants to compare, say Expt and Ctrl for the experimental and control populations. A useful effect size measure is Cohen's *d*: *d* describes the difference in means between two populations, $\mu_{\text{Expt}} - \mu_{\text{Ctrl}}$ for example, in terms of the standard deviation, σ , which is assumed the same for both populations; that is, $d = (\mu_{\text{Expt}} - \mu_{\text{Ctrl}}) / \sigma$. (Usually, the σ is in terms of the experimental unit (EU)). However, for this paper, we consider two different σ when speaking of *d*; therefore, we will add a subscript to *d* to indicate the referencing σ .) Cohen's *d* may be easier to understand than the often-used Cohen's *f*. Cohen's *f* describes the variability among multiple population means (σ_μ) in terms of σ ; thus, a ratio of standard deviations. [Figure 4](#) provides examples of Cohen's *d* and *f* in the context of splenic CD4 percentages compared among 3 populations.⁵ The second reason to simplify power analyses to independent samples *t*-tests is that as the number of groups increases, the power for detecting a specific value of *d* also increases. (This is because the overall sample size increases, even though the size of the two groups being compared remains the same.) Hence, the power computed from

an independent samples *t*-test when there are 3 or more groups is the lowest the power will be for detecting a specific *d* value comparing an *a priori* specified pair of means.

Figure 4. Cohen’s effect size examples for comparing means (μ s) between 2 populations (Cohen’s *d*) and among ≥ 2 populations (Cohen’s *f*). The example outcome is the percentage of splenic CD4 cells, assumed to be normal in distribution with the animals in each population having a standard deviation (σ_A) of 4.5 percentage points. Cohen’s *d* is the distance between 2 means divided by σ_A ; *d* is in σ_A units. Cohen’s *f* is the standard deviation of the populations’ means (σ_μ) divided by σ_A . In all panels, the *f* and *d* values are mathematically equivalent, noting that the number of *d* values is one fewer than the number of population means being compared. Across all panels, Cohen’s *f* is constant to illustrate how its interpretation is more complicated than interpreting Cohen’s *d* values. (A) Hypothesized means for 2 populations. (B) Hypothesized means for 3 populations with the dispersion of the means at its mathematical minimum and (C) at its mathematical maximum for the given Cohen’s *f* value.⁵ Note: This explanation assumes that any extra variability (like variability among cages, σ_C) has been accounted for in the comparisons.

For an independent samples *t*-test, there are 6 parameters in a power analysis:

- (i) sample size, $N = n_{\text{Expt}} + n_{\text{Ctrl}}$, with n_{Expt} usually assumed to be the same as n_{Ctrl} ;

- (ii) power, $1 - \beta$, where β is the probability of a Type II error;
- (iii) significance level α , where α is the probability of a Type I error;
- (iv*) the population means of group Expt, μ_{Expt} , and
- (v*) of group Ctrl, μ_{Ctrl} ; and
- (vi*) the standard deviation of the experimental unit, σ_{EU} .

* We may combine the last 3 with Cohen's $d_{\text{EU}} = (\mu_{\text{Expt}} - \mu_{\text{Ctrl}}) / \sigma_{\text{EU}}$, so that there are effectively only 4 parameters.

- (iv) standardized effect size, d_{EU} .

Power analyses are appropriately performed before data are collected and analyzed; not after.²⁰ To perform a power analysis, we must decide which single parameter we want to calculate; for example, the standardized effect size, d_{EU} , or the group sample size, n . Then, we must assume actual values for the remaining parameters; we give examples below.

Many readers may already know these basic power analysis facts for an independent samples t -test, but when the animal experiment is like our typical experiment with the distinguishing characteristic of same-group cage-mates, the definition of N is the total number of cages (henceforth, N_{cage}) and experimental unit's standard deviation, σ_{EU} , is in terms of σ_{C} and σ_{A} (these two standard deviations defined in Eqn 2). These definitions introduce new parameters to be included in the power analyses. Specifically, since there are multiple animals per cage, we need to specify m – the number of same-group animals that will be in each cage. We will assume that m is the same for all cages, and that the total number of animals needed for the experiment is $N_{\text{cage}} \times m$. (Note: Sometimes we know ahead of time that the number of animals per cage will differ among cages. In these instances, we may assume an average m for all cages, noting that the average need not be an integer.) For σ_{EU} , we also need a value for σ_{C} because the parameter, σ_{EU} , is a function of σ_{C} , m , and the animal variability, σ_{A} : $\sigma_{\text{EU}} = \sqrt{[\sigma_{\text{C}}^2 + (\sigma_{\text{A}}^2/m)]}$. To date, it is likely very rare that a biomedical researcher will have an informed estimate of σ_{C} since so few report such estimates. To simplify the assumption process, we speak of the cage variability in terms of the intraclass correlation, ρ – the proportion of the total variance that comes from the variability among the cages; i.e., $\rho = \sigma_{\text{C}}^2 / (\sigma_{\text{C}}^2 + \sigma_{\text{A}}^2)$. Typically, ρ is constrained to values in 0 to 1, but negative values are possible.⁷ Speaking in terms of ρ will also standardize the following formulae to those in other research areas; for example, clinical and educational studies, and livestock breeding. Specifically, $\sigma_{\text{C}}^2 = \rho / (1 - \rho)$. We can then write the standard deviation of the experimental unit as

$$\sigma_{\text{EU}} = \sigma_{\text{A}} \sqrt{\frac{\rho}{(1-\rho)} + \frac{1}{m}}. \quad (3)$$

Effect size calculations

In many instances, there are constraints (usually financial) on the number of animals and likely the number of cages that can be used for a given experiment. In these instances, we calculate a detectable effect size, d_{EU} , assuming reasonable power and significance levels and a set number of animals. Here, we give an example of how to perform an effect size calculation in

JASP and then convert that effect size, which is in terms of σ_{EU} , into an effect size in terms of the standard deviation of the animals, σ_A .

We target a power of 0.80 on a 0.05 significance level independent samples t -test of $H_0: \mu_{Expt} = \mu_{Ctrl}$. We have 24 mice that will be equally randomized to groups Control and Experimental. We will consider two caging schemes: $m = 2$ mice per cage with $N_{cage} = 12$ cages equally split between the two groups (or $n_{Expt} = n_{Ctrl}$); and $m = 4$ per cage with $n_{Expt} = n_{Ctrl}$ and a total of $N_{cage} = 6$ cages. See [Figure 5](#) for the two proposed experiment designs and their descriptions. We can now compute the effect sizes for each design.

A					B			
Rack	Col 1	Col 2	Col 3	Col 4	Rack	Col 1	Col 2	Col 3
Row 1	C C	E E	E E	E E	Row 1	C C	E E	E E
Row 2	C C	C C	C C	C C		C C	E E	E E
Row 3	E E	E E	C C	E E	Row 2	C C	C C	E E
						C C	C C	E E

Figure 5. 24 same-sex, unrelated mice of the same age will be equally randomized to treatment groups, Control (C) and Experimental (E). **(A)** The first 2 mice randomized to a group will be individually administered the treatment and placed in the same cage; remaining sets of 2 same-group mice will be similarly treated and caged. **(B)** The first 4 mice randomized to a group will be individually administered the treatment and placed in the same cage; remaining sets of 4 same-group mice will be similarly treated and caged. For both experiment designs, the cages will then be randomized on the rack.

For the $m = 2$ housing scheme, in JASP, we use the **Power** module, with these settings.

Statistical test: Independent Samples T-Test

I want to calculate the ... Effect size

Minimal desired power: 0.8

Type I error rate: 0.05

Sample size per group: 6 (recall, here sample size is in terms of cages, not animals)

Sample size ratio: 1

Alternative Hypothesis: Two-sided.

In the results from JASP, we see Cohen's d_{EU} is 1.796.

Now we update the module for the $m = 4$ housing scheme, changing only the **Sample size per group** from 6 cages to 3 cages. The updated Cohen's d_{EU} is 3.071.

Often, when working with Cohen's d , animal researchers expect d to be in terms of the animal variability, σ_A . We can convert Cohen's d_{EU} in σ_{EU} units to σ_A units by replacing σ_{EU} with the right-hand-side of Eqn 3 to get

$$d_A = d_{EU} \sqrt{\frac{\rho}{(1-\rho)} + \frac{1}{m}} \quad (4)$$

We did not need to assume a value for ρ to compute the original d_{EU} in our two examples above, but to interpret d_A , we will need to assume a value for ρ . Without any preliminary results, a conservative strategy for assuming a value for ρ is to choose a larger value rather than a smaller one. Here, we will assume that $\rho = 0.2$ and plug it and m and d_{EU} (from JASP results) into Eqn 4. For the $m = 2$ caging scheme, $d_A = 1.796 \sqrt{[(0.2 / (1 - 0.2)) + (1 / 2)]} = 1.56$; and for the $m = 4$ caging scheme, $d_A = 3.071 \sqrt{[(0.2 / (1 - 0.2)) + (1 / 4)]} = 2.17$. This means that the $m = 2$ caging scheme will detect a smaller d_A with the available 24 mice than the $m = 4$ caging scheme. [Figure 6A](#) illustrates how d_A increases with assumed ρ in animal-number-equivalent $m = 2$ and $m = 4$ caging schemes. In general, regardless of $\rho > 0$, when the total number of animals is the same for a more-cages & fewer-animals experiment and a fewer-cages & more-animals experiment, the more-cages & fewer-animals experiment is more efficient because it can detect a smaller d_A .

Sample size calculations

Suppose we want to compute the sample size needed to detect a $d_A = 1.2$ with 0.80 power using a 0.05 significance level test. (Note: If the mice are singly housed, then the usual ANOVA or independent samples t -test is appropriate; and $n_{Ctrl} = 12$ and $n_{Expt} = 12$, with $N_{cage} = 24$ overall, will provide 0.80 power for detecting a $d_A = 1.2$ using a 0.05 significance level test.) We will consider experiment designs like those in [Figure 5](#); that is, $m = 2$ and $m = 4$ caging schemes. Unlike for the effect size calculations, we will need to assume ρ beforehand, because we need ρ and the planned m to convert d_A to d_{EU} . We take Eqn 4 and solve d_{EU} to get

$$d_{EU} = \frac{d_A}{\sqrt{\frac{\rho}{1-\rho} + \frac{1}{m}}} \quad (5)$$

As before, we will assume $\rho = 0.2$. For the $m = 2$ caging scheme, plugging d_A , ρ , and m into Eqn 5, we get $d_{EU} = 1.2 / \sqrt{[(0.2 / (1 - 0.2)) + (1 / 2)]} = 1.39$. In JASP, we use the Power module to compute the number of *cages* needed for detecting $d_{EU} = 1.39$. These are the settings:

Statistical test: Independent Samples T-Test

I want to calculate the ... Sample Size N (the number of cages)

Minimal effect size of interest: 1.39

Minimal desired power: 0.8

Type I error rate: 0.05

Sample size ratio: 1

Alternative Hypothesis: Two-sided.

In the results from JASP, we see the cage number calculation is 10 cages for each group; thus 20 cages overall, and with 2 mice per cage, that is a total of 40 mice.

Figure 6. For all panels, power is targeted at 0.80 on a two-sided test comparing 2 means and conducted at the 0.05 significance level within a LMM (Eqn 2). The assumed experiment designs are like those in [Figure 4](#). **(A)** Effect size, d_A varies by ρ . Two animal-number-equivalent caging schemes are compared. Smaller d_A is preferred. **(B)** Sample size varies by ρ . Sample sizes are counts of cages and animals needed per group to detect a $d_A = 1.2$. Two power-equivalent caging schemes are compared. Smaller counts are preferred. **(C)** The breakpoint day, D_{BP} , varies by ρ . D_{BP} is for the two power-equivalent caging schemes in panel B. Experiments ending before D_{BP} are cheaper when cages contain 2 animals; otherwise caging 4 animals per cage will be cheaper. D_{BP} assumes the cost of a single animal is 25 times greater than the per diem cost of a single cage; i.e., the costs ratio is 25. Though not illustrated, D_{BP} increases as the costs ratio increases. A costs ratio of 25 is quite small for our institution, so we would expect to be D_{BP} further out in most cases. R code used to produce figure values is in the Supplementary Material.

For the $m = 4$ caging scheme, plugging d_A , ρ , and m into Eqn 5, we get $d_{EU} = 1.2 / \sqrt{[(0.2 / (1 - 0.2)) + (1 / 4)]} = 1.70$. We update the Minimal effect size of interest setting in the Power module of JASP to 1.70. The computed number of cages is 7 for each of the 2 groups; thus, 4 mice/cage \times 14 cages = 56 mice. This means that the $m = 2$ caging scheme requiring 40 mice is a more efficient experiment design: both caging schemes have the same power (i.e., power-equivalent), but the $m = 2$ caging scheme uses fewer animals. [Figure 6B](#) illustrates how numbers of cages and animals in a group increase with assumed ρ in the power-equivalent $m = 2$ and $m = 4$ caging schemes. In general, regardless of $\rho > 0$, more-cages & fewer-animals experiments will require fewer animals overall than fewer-cages & more-animals experiments. [Table 1](#) provides calculated sample sizes for select caging schemes (i.e., m same-group animals per cage) over a range of d_A effect sizes assuming target power values of 0.8 and 0.9 and a significance level of 0.05. The calculations also assume ρ values of 0.10 and 0.20. The choice of these ρ values is based on results from two large cage enrichment studies in female mice; we provide more details below.

Table 1. Sample size calculations for n_{cage} , the number of cages needed per group^a, to detect a difference of d_A between the means of two populations with the indicated power on a 0.05 significance level independent samples t -test. The calculations are made for caging schemes with m same-group mice per cage and for two values of ρ . The total number of animals per group is given by $m \times n_{\text{cage}}$. The assumed experiment design is as described in [Figure 5](#). R code that produces tabular values is in the Supplementary Material.

Power	d_A	$\rho = 0.10$				$\rho = 0.20$			
		$m = 2$	$m = 3$	$m = 4$	$m = 5$	$m = 2$	$m = 3$	$m = 4$	$m = 5$
0.80	0.50	39.5	29	24	21	48.5	38	32.5	29.5
	0.75	18.5	13.5	11.5	10	22	17.5	15	14
	1.00	11	8.5	7	6.5	13	10.5	9	8.5
	1.25	7.5	6	5	4.5	9	7	6.5	6
	1.50	5.5	4.5	4	3.5	6.5	5.5	5	4.5
	1.75	4.5	4	3.5	3	5.5	4.5	4	4
	2.00	4	3.5	3	3	4.5	4	3.5	3.5
0.90	0.50	52.5	38.5	31.5	27.5	64.5	50.5	43.5	39
	0.75	24	18	15	13	29.5	23	20	18
	1.00	14	10.5	9	8	17	13.5	12	11
	1.25	9.5	7.5	6.5	5.5	11.5	9	8	7.5
	1.50	7	5.5	5	4.5	8.5	7	6	5.5
	1.75	5.5	4.5	4	3.5	6.5	5.5	5	4.5
	2.00	4.5	4	3.5	3.5	5.5	4.5	4	4

^a The total number of cages needed for the experiment is the number of groups multiplied by n_{cage} . The groups need not be balanced with respect to n_{cage} or the number of animals per group, though approximate balance is preferred.

An example of using [Table 1](#): Suppose we will have 3 treatment groups and cannot mix groups in a cage. We plan to house $m = 2$ same-group rats per cage. We want to detect a $d_A = 1.50$ between a pair of treatment means with 0.90 power on a 0.05 significance level test. We conservatively choose $\rho = 0.2$. From [Table 1](#), we will need 8.5 cages per group; thus 25.5 cages altogether. So as to not drop below 0.90 power, or house any rat singly, we round up to 26 cages. Two group will have 9 cages and one group 8 cages; the total number of rats will be 52.

We performed a simulation to determine whether power was at the stated levels in [Table 1](#) (for those settings where cages per group were less than 30). In all cases, simulated power was at least at the stated level (see Supplementary Material).

Assuming ρ values for power analyses

A priori sample size calculations require assumed parameter values for the often-unknown parameters, d_A and ρ . The more we can narrow down our knowledge about where values of d_A and ρ are, the more accurate our target power (also assumed in the sample size calculation) will be to the future results. For d_A , Lenth provides strategies for obtaining informed d_A values,¹⁹ and Zhang & Hartmann provide examples on how to use previous studies to obtain d_A values.³⁷ However, for obtaining informed ρ values, since very few, if any, have reported estimated ρ values in animal experiments, we seem left with the strategy of assuming a larger ρ value to

better ensure our true power is enough. But still, having some idea of how ρ can vary among different outcomes may be of use, even if our particular outcome or maybe even our species was not covered. To this end, [Tables 2](#) and [3](#) contain estimated ρ values for some behavioral outcome variables and body and organs weights from mice. The data came from two large cage enrichment studies in mice.^{1,36} The Supplementary Material describes the methods used to estimate these ρ values.

Table 2. Estimated intraclass correlations (ρ) and 90% confidence intervals for body and organ weights and a stress hormone from Bailoo et al (2018). Estimates are based on 32 cages.

Outcome	C57BL/6	SWISS
Week 1 ^a weight	-0.19 (NA)	0.03 (-0.12, 0.22)
Week 2 ^a weight	-0.04 (-0.25, 0.09)	0.11 (0.01, 0.37)
Week 3 ^a weight	-0.11 (-0.32, -0.09)	0.13 (0.01, 0.38)
Week 4 ^a weight	-0.09 (-0.31, -0.04)	0.11 (0.00, 0.35)
Week 5 ^a weight	0.16 (0.07, 0.46)	0.26 (0.03, 0.42)
Week 6 ^a weight	0.28 (0.16, 0.52)	0.11 (0.01, 0.37)
Week 7 ^a weight	0.06 (-0.04, 0.34)	0.23 (0.06, 0.43)
Week 8 ^a weight	-0.01 (-0.18, 0.15)	0.15 (0.04, 0.39)
Body ^b weight	0.21 (0.11, 0.57)	0.28 (0.08, 0.49)
Brain ^b weight	0.38 (0.22, 0.62)	0.45 (0.29, 0.65)
Heart ^b weight	0.66 (0.37, 0.78)	0.43 (0.15, 0.80)
Kidney ^b , left weight	0.62 (0.31, 0.77)	0.43 (0.29, 0.64)
Kidney ^b , right weight	0.24 (0.09, 0.67)	0.49 (0.30, 0.67)
Liver ^b weight	0.51 (0.30, 0.69)	0.31 (0.21, 0.55)
Spleen ^b weight	0.62 (0.30, 0.77)	0.16 (0.07, 0.47)
Adrenal ^b , left weight	0.39 (0.26, 0.62)	0.15 (0.05, 0.42)
Adrenal ^b , right weight	0.20 (0.10, 0.48)	0.07 (-0.05, 0.33)
Fecal corticosterone	0.67 (0.32, 0.78)	0.15 (0.06, 0.47)

^a Mice were between 31-34 days old at the start of the experiment (Week 1). ^b Mice were between 19-19.5 weeks old at the end of the experiment. Weights were recorded in grams and corticosterone was recorded in ng/0.05 g of feces. Details of the data and statistical estimation of ρ are in the Supplementary Material.

Table 3. Estimated intracluster correlations (ρ) and 90% confidence intervals for behaviors from Wolfer et al (2004). Estimates are based on 36 cages.

Behavior test	Behavior	C57BL/6	DBA/2	F1 Hybrid ^a
O-maze	Head dips/min	0.23 (0.17, 0.43)	0.34 (0.26, 0.54)	0.30 (0.23, 0.50)
	% protected head dips	0.17 (0.13, 0.37)	0.00 (-0.10, 0.16)	0.23 (0.09, 0.52)
	% open arm entries	0.11 (0.05, 0.37)	0.04 (-0.04, 0.23)	0.28 (0.22, 0.53)
	Fecal bolus count	NA	0.18 (0.12, 0.40)	0.09 (0.03, 0.35)
	Path traveled (m/min)	0.16 (0.11, 0.43)	0.06 (-0.02, 0.28)	0.34 (0.20, 0.60)
Open field	Center avoidance 1st 10 min (m)	0.23 (0.18, 0.44)	0.20 (0.16, 0.39)	0.11 (0.05, 0.34)
	Center avoidance habituation (m)	0.23 (0.16, 0.46)	0.03 (-0.05, 0.22)	0.18 (0.13, 0.38)
	Path traveled 1st 10 min (m)	0.27 (0.21, 0.49)	0.20 (0.13, 0.41)	0.34 (0.28, 0.56)
	Path traveled habituation (m)	0.25 (0.18, 0.48)	0.09 (0.03, 0.33)	0.43 (0.31, 0.59)
	% time running/walking	0.25 (0.19, 0.50)	0.19 (0.15, 0.41)	0.43 (0.36, 0.61)
Novel object	Horizontal object exploration (m/min)	0.11 (0.05, 0.41)	0.08 (0.02, 0.30)	0.09 (0.03, 0.35)
	Vertical object exploration (m/min)	0.16 (0.10, 0.45)	0.05 (-0.03, 0.26)	0.06 (-0.01, 0.26)
	% path in object zone	-0.03 (-0.11, 0.07)	0.06 (-0.01, 0.30)	0.13 (0.08, 0.34)
	Object exploration distance (m)	0.05 (-0.06, 0.47)	0.03 (-0.06, 0.22)	0.05 (-0.04, 0.32)
	Corner distance (m)	0.23 (0.16, 0.48)	0.07 (0.00, 0.35)	0.15 (0.10, 0.49)
Morris water maze	Swim path length (m)	-0.07 (-0.20, -0.02)	-0.09 (-0.19, -0.08)	-0.08 (-0.21, -0.05)
	% time near wall	0.01 (-0.09, 0.17)	-0.03 (-0.13, 0.08)	0.07 (0.01, 0.31)
	Average swim speed (m/s)	-0.03 (-0.15, 0.07)	0.12 (0.06, 0.32)	0.01 (-0.09, 0.18)
	Probe: annulus crossings	0.09 (0.03, 0.33)	0.11 (0.05, 0.34)	0.03 (-0.06, 0.22)
	Probe: target proximity	-0.05 (-0.19, 0.02)	0.09 (0.03, 0.35)	0.11 (0.05, 0.32)

^a F1 Hybrids are a cross from C57BL/6 and DBA/2. Details of the data and statistical estimation of ρ are in the Supplementary Material.

COST ANALYSES

The following cost analyses are based on a simple fee structure, where costs can be dichotomized into per animal costs and per diem cage costs. Though fee structures can widely differ from one institution to another, it is very often the case that cost of a single animal (including all the effort and resources that go into collecting data from that single animal) is many times more than the animal husbandry cost (e.g., housing, feeding, and generally caring for the welfare of the animal). For example, currently a cage per diem charge may be between \$0.90 – \$2.00 USD, compared to the \$30 USD cost of a 3-week-old C57BL/6 mouse, which doesn't include any time or resources spent in gathering data from the animal. That noted, often, researchers will put as many animals in a cage as allowed by animal ethics committees (e.g., IACUCs). One reason they do this is to reduce cage costs, especially for those fee structures that charge by the cage instead of animal. But the animals themselves frequently cost a great deal more than cage costs. When we have two power-equivalent experiments, one with more-cages & fewer-animals overall and the other with fewer-cages & more-animals overall, we need to be able to compare experiment costs. A simple formula for experiment cost of one experiment has these 5 parameters: N_A – total number of animals; C_A – cost per animal; N_{cage} – total number of cages; C_{cage} – per diem cost of a cage; and D – length of the experiment in days. The formula is

$$\text{Cost} = (N_A \times C_A) + (N_{\text{cage}} \times C_{\text{cage}} \times D). \quad (6)$$

After determining the sample size, we can know N_{cage} and N_A for a given detectable d_A . The per diem cage cost, C_{cage} , is usually dictated by the animal facility or some other entity. The researcher gets to determine the length of the experiment, D . The remaining parameter, per animal cost, C_A , is partly determined by outside entities (e.g., vendors, in-house breeders) and partly by the researcher. The part of C_A determined by the researcher should include the cost of procedures, assays, and other resources, as well as how much time it takes to obtain measures of all the outcome variables to be taken from a single animal. C_A can vary widely from experiment to experiment. Once values for each of these parameters are determined, we use Eqn 6 to calculate the cost.

In the sample size calculation example above, we learned that the $m = 2$ caging scheme required fewer animals overall, but more cages, than the power-equivalent $m = 4$ caging scheme. How do the costs compare between these two experiment designs?

Continuing the sample size calculation example, suppose $C_A = 50$ USD, and $C_{\text{cage}} = 2$ USD, and the experiment will last $D = 30$ days. Here are the costs for the two caging schemes:

$m = 2$.) $40 \text{ mice} \times 50 \text{ USD/mouse} + 20 \text{ cages} \times 2 \text{ USD}/(\text{cage} \times \text{day}) \times 30 \text{ days} = 3,200 \text{ USD}$

$m = 4$.) $56 \text{ mice} \times 50 \text{ USD/mouse} + 14 \text{ cages} \times 2 \text{ USD}/(\text{cage} \times \text{day}) \times 30 \text{ days} = 3,640 \text{ USD}$

The $m = 2$ cage scheme is more cost effective than the $m = 4$ scheme. Even though the $m = 2$ scheme has more cages, the reduction in total number of mice offsets the cage costs. But if the length of the experiment were to be $D = 90$ days, then the $m = 4$ scheme would be less expensive at 5,320 USD compared to 5,600 USD for the $m = 2$ scheme. This raises the question: How long would the experiment need to be for the cage costs of the $m = 2$ scheme to overwhelm the animal costs of the $m = 4$ scheme? This is to ask, at what point in time is the cost of one experiment design (ED1) equal to the cost of a second experiment design (ED2). Because ED1 and ED2 are

power equivalent, we can use Eqn 6 and set $\text{Cost}^{(\text{ED1})} = \text{Cost}^{(\text{ED2})}$, then we solve for D which we call the Break-Point Day, D_{BP} :

$$D_{\text{BP}} = \left[\frac{C_A}{C_{\text{cage}}} \right] \times \left[\frac{N_A^{(\text{ED1})} - N_A^{(\text{ED2})}}{N_{\text{cage}}^{(\text{ED2})} - N_{\text{cage}}^{(\text{ED1})}} \right] \quad (7)$$

Continuing our example, with ED1 as the $m = 2$ caging scheme and ED2 the $m = 4$ scheme, the costs of the two experiments are the same at $D_{\text{BP}} = [50/2] \times [(56 - 40) / (20 - 14)] = 66.7$ days. So, if the experiment is 68 or more days longer, it would be cheaper to go with the $m = 4$ scheme.

A few observations about Eqn 7: First, often the cost of a single animal is many times more than the per diem cage cost; thus the “costs ratio” (the left-hand factor in Eqn 7) tends to have the most impact on extending D_{BP} . Secondly, the “count differentials ratio” (the right-hand factor in Eqn 7) is determined by the sample size calculations and depends on the assumed value of ρ . When the count differentials ratio is 0, then animal numbers are equal, and the design with fewer cages is always cheaper. When the count differentials ratio is undefined (0 in the denominator), then the number of cages are equal, and the design with fewer animals is always cheaper. Third, Eqn 7 has the counts differential ratio in terms of total numbers of animals and cages, but if all groups are balanced with respect to cage count and m animals per cage, then we may use the count differentials ratio on the per-group counts and still arrive at the same D_{BP} . [Figure 6C](#) illustrates how D_{BP} changes with assumed ρ in the power-equivalent $m = 2$ and $m = 4$ caging schemes from the example above. Because the required counts of cages and animals increase in step-like increments as ρ increases, the calculated D_{BP} does not strictly increase but can go up and then down. However, in general, as ρ increases the minimum D_{BP} increases; that is, it takes more time for the caging cost in the more-cages & fewer-animals experiments to overwhelm the animal cost in power-equivalent fewer-cages & more-animals experiments. Lastly, if the per diem charges are based on individual animals instead of a cage (or some other larger unit that contains multiple animals), then the experiment design with the smaller number of animals will always be cheaper than a power-equivalent experiment design with more animals.

DISCUSSION

Many animal experiments have the experiment design characteristic of same-group cage-mates. This characteristic has implications on appropriate statistical and power analyses, and consequently, experiment costs. Usual statistical analyses like ANOVA and independent samples t -tests may not be appropriate. Appropriate analyses will account for potential cage variability. Linear mixed models (LMMs) can account for cage variability. For statistical analyses, unique cage identifiers need to be collected as part of the data and these identifiers used in the analyses.

When comparing an appropriate LMM analysis to a usual ANOVA analysis, they return the same results when cage variability is negligible (i.e., estimated to be 0). But seldom can we know whether cage variability is potentially negligible until we fit the LMM; hence, the LMM should be the first analysis to consider. In same-group cage-mates experiments, even when the animals are individually (randomized and) treated, non-negligible intracluster correlation makes

the cage the effective experimental unit, rather than the animal. For power analyses involving the LMM, the cage, rather than the animal, is the relevant experimental unit. It follows that experiment designs with more cages housing fewer animals per cage are statistically more efficient than experiment designs with fewer cages housing more animals per cage – the same conclusion as for cluster randomized trials in humans.²⁶

From the cost analyses comparing two power-equivalent designs (same power, different sample sizes), a possibly surprising result is that more cages housing fewer animals per cage can also be more cost effective than loading cages up with the maximum number of animals allowed. But depending on how long the experiment is to last, the cheaper experiment can change, and we can possibly compute that break-point day, D_{BP} , at which that switch in cost effectiveness occurs. Regardless of whether animal husbandry costs are charged per cage (or pen or tank) or animal or some other fee structure, animal husbandry costs are very often a small portion of the total cost of an animal experiment. This means that if we can reduce the total number of animals by even a few animals, the cost savings from fewer animals will likely offset any potential increase in animal husbandry costs because of more-cages & fewer-animals per cage.

Power and cost analyses depend on assumed cage variability, σ_C . We simplify this assumption to the intracluster correlation, ρ , which is the proportion of total variability that comes from cage variability (i.e., $\rho = \sigma_C^2 / (\sigma_C^2 + \sigma_A^2)$, where σ_C is the cage standard deviation and σ_A the animal standard deviation). Since usual power analyses so often consider effect sizes in terms of only σ_A (i.e., d_A), and since power analyses for same-group cage-mates experiments require effect sizes in terms of the σ_{EU} , (i.e., d_{EU}), we use ρ to convert d_{EU} into d_A so that we can perform effect size and sample size calculations. With an assumed ρ , we can calculate sample sizes for two or more experiment designs (e.g., 2 animals per cage vs 4 animals per cage); those designs will be power-equivalent. Costs of more-cages & fewer-animals designs will be lower than power equivalent fewer-cages & more-animals designs up to a break-point day, D_{BP} ; and that D_{BP} increases as ρ increases and as the total cost of the individual animals increase.

Regarding animal welfare: In the case where the length of an experiment exceeds the D_{BP} break-point, and the fewer-cages & more animals experiment is cheaper than the more-cages & fewer-animals one, we believe that the Reduce principle of the 3Rs of ethical animal research is more important than the saved financial cost. Furthermore, the more-cages & fewer-animals design has less inflation of Type I error if cage variability is ignored in the statistical model.^{16,38}

Still on animal welfare, the extreme of more-cages & fewer-animals is single housing. Indeed, single housing is optimal with respect to statistical power and cost and fulfills the Reduce principle of the 3Rs of animal research. But many species of research animals are social, meaning that housing multiple animals in the same cage is better for their welfare than single housing. The stress inflicted on singly-housed animals may unintentionally bias the results of the experiment. We do not recommend single housing of social laboratory animal species based only on statistical reasons.

On intracluster correlation (ρ): When animals are exposed to the same microenvironment (as in a cage, enclosure, or tank), their outcomes may become correlated. For those outcomes, often correlation will develop over time. Taking a human example, consider how correlation of an academic outcome may change over the course of a school year in classes of kindergartners randomized to a particular educational treatment. But sometimes, correlation may develop immediately. Taking a human example, consider the correlation that may be induced in surgery

outcomes when patients randomized to a particular surgical treatment have the same surgical team perform the surgery in a multi-site clinical trial. Accounting for cage in the statistical analyses will provide an estimate of cage variability (σ_C) from which we can compute the estimated ρ . However, the estimated ρ is just that – an estimate. Whether the estimated ρ is 0 or not does not guarantee the true state of intraclass correlation (“There is none.” vs “There is some.”). Indeed, the distribution of estimated ρ s can vary widely in small experiments. Even though there can be a large amount of variability in the estimated ρ values, more-cages & fewer-animal experiments will provide more precise estimates of the true ρ than fewer-cages & more-animal experiments. In the end, a conservative statistical approach is to account for cage variability, and a statistically efficient design will have more-cages & fewer-animals.

Regarding same-group vs mixed-group cage-mates: This article deals only with same-group cage-mates experiments. Some experiments can have mixed-group cage-mates, where cage-mates are in different experimental groups. Mixed-group cage-mates experiments are a type of randomized block design, where cage is a block. Intraclass correlation among mixed-group cage-mates can also exist, and as in same-group cage-mates experiments, that correlation also manifests as cage variability (i.e., $\sigma_C > 0$). When possible, mixed-group cage-mates experiments are recommended over same-group cage-mates experiments: mixed-group cage-mates experiments are more statistically powerful and broaden the generalizability of the results.^{10,12,34} However, just as in same-group cage-mates experiments, unique cage identifiers need to be recorded and used in the analyses to reap the power gains; because ignoring cage in the analyses of mixed-group cage-mates experiments can cause an increase in false negative results (i.e., Type II errors); the p -values tend to be too large.

On statistical software: We demonstrated how to perform both statistical and power analyses for same-group cage-mates experiments using JASP – a free, open-source statistical software designed for non-statisticians. In addition to the wide-spread availability of JASP to research communities, JASP files can be saved to allow others to verify computational reproducibility. JASP also produces R code for its analyses which opens up verification of computational reproducibility to a wider audience than only those who can use JASP. For statistical analyses, the Supplementary Material contains R and SAS code for fitting the LMM model in Eqn 2. Though effect size and sample size calculations can be performed in JASP, those calculations can only happen for one set of assumed parameters at a time. The Supplementary Material contains R code for performing effect size and sample size calculations over a range of assumed parameters, as presented in [Figure 6](#) and [Table 1](#). We heavily commented this R code in hopes that someone without any R experience can run the code in a web-based R browser. A future direction is to develop an R Shiny application that will perform these calculations without the need for the user to run R code.

On generalizability. The ideas and statistical methods to account for cluster variability mostly come out of agricultural and epidemiological sciences.^{22,25} We adapt them for laboratory animal experiments here. Our working context and examples have been in laboratory mice, where we observed and assumed ρ to be primarily between 0.10 – 0.30 (which is 10 – 30% of total variability coming from cages). Other species, housing setups, and outcome variables will have different ranges of ρ . Whether cage (or enclosure or cluster) variability is negligible or substantial, adopting the linear mixed model approach recommended here appropriately accommodates both situations. And, when the experiment has the same-group cage-mates characteristic, adopting the experiment design recommendations of more-cages & fewer-animals

for other species of laboratory animals commonly group housed (e.g., fish, frogs, rabbits, dogs, non-human primates) can allow for reductions in animal numbers and in potential Type 1 errors if cage is inadvertently ignored in the statistical analyses.

On limitations: This article has considered only normally distributed outcome variables. The statistical advantages of more-cages & fewer-animals experiments over fewer-cages & more-animals experiments will be the same for outcome variables that are not normal in distribution (e.g., binomial, Poisson, and time-to-event outcome variables); such analyses are covered in the context of human studies.²⁵ Using a linear mixed model (LMM) on these non-normal outcome variables will give biased results. Another limitation is that estimates of the intracluster correlation, ρ , can vary widely when there are very few cages. This article has also only considered a simple same-group cages-mates experiment design (Figures 1 and 5), which assumes that all cages are completely randomized within the same location (e.g., in a single animal room with cages randomized to open spots on available cage racks). Though many animal experiments have the same-group cage-mates characteristic in the experiment design, the designs can be more complicated than the example in this article. The planned statistical analyses that accompany those more complicated designs should account for the other controlled and known factors and include the cage identifiers to account for cage variability. Usually, the addition of the cage identifier in the statistical model does not add any more complication to the statistical analysis plan than that described in Eqn 2. However, when there are very few cages, estimates of ρ can vary widely.

In conclusion, when an experiment has the same-group cage-mates characteristic, cage identifiers should be included in the statistical analysis, and more-cages & fewer-animals tends to be better than fewer-cages & more-animals with respect to power and costs. These recommendations can improve the scientific quality of animal experiments by reducing false positives and improving reproducibility. Equally important, they can enable researchers to adhere to the 3Rs by using fewer animals without sacrificing results. Adopting such approaches will benefit researchers (through more reliable data), institutions (through cost savings), and animals (through reduction in numbers required).

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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The author declares no conflicts of interest.

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